

Professional Commitment of Primary School Teachers of Sikkim

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Abstract

The present study is on Professional Commitment of Primary School Teachers of Sikkim. Quantitative research method was employed. The sample of 100 primary school teachers was selected from Gangtok and Mangan District of Sikkim. Out of 100 teachers 50 male and 50 female, 50 probationary and 50 regular, 50 urban and 50 rural teachers were selected. The sample was collected by way of Random Sampling Techniques. The findings of the study suggested that there exist no difference in the male and female, probationary and regular, rural and urban primary school teachers with respect to professional commitment. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that Male and female, probationary and regular, rural and urban secondary school teachers are equally committed towards their profession.

Keywords: Professional Commitment, Urban and Rural, Probationary and Regular

1. Introduction

Professional commitment of school teachers relates to their dedication, responsibility, and involvement in their field. It refers to their commitment to go above and beyond fundamental job responsibilities in order to strengthen learning for pupils, academic results, and the school environment. Key elements of professional dedication include:

Dedication to Student Learning: entails ensuring that students obtain a quality education by developing effective lesson plans, employing creative teaching approaches, and addressing varied learning requirements.

Continuous Professional Development: entails lifetime learning, attending training sessions, seeking higher education, and keeping up with the most recent educational trends and innovations.

Ethical Responsibility: involves practicing professional ethics, being fair, and creating a healthy and respectful teaching atmosphere.

Collaboration and teamwork: involves collaborating with colleagues, parents, and the community to establish a helpful educational environment.

Passion for Teaching: entails demonstrating enthusiasm for the subject and motivating students to attain academic and personal success.

Adaptability and resilience: require adapting to new educational regulations, curricular changes, and problems in the classroom.

Commitment to School Improvement: Participating in extracurricular activities, school committees, and initiatives that boost the institution's performance in general.

1.1. Significance of the study

Teachers play an important part in any country's educational systems. Teachers are ultimately responsible for determining a country's progress and are hence often referred to as nation builders. The teacher is the essential part of the educational system, carrying out a variety of crucial obligations. Early childhood educators are crucial in forming young children's core educational experiences. Their dedication to their work has a direct effect on students' entire personality development, mental health, and academic growth; their professional commitment is critical in developing well-rounded individuals who become responsible citizens. Their commitment to teaching not only enhances student outcomes, but also strengthens the education system and society at large. Investing in teachers' professional development and well-being is critical to maintaining their dedication and improving educational quality.

1.2. Statement of the problems

In this context, the investigator made an earnest effort to find the professional commitment among Primary School Teachers.

Hence, the problem is stated as, **“Professional Commitment among Primary School Teachers of Sikkim”**.

1.3. Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To find out the Professional commitment between Male and Female Primary School teachers.
2. To find out the professional commitment between Probationary and Regular Primary School Teachers.
3. To find out the professional commitment between Urban and Rural Primary School Teachers.

1.4. Hypotheses of the study

The hypotheses of the study are as follows:

1. There is no significant difference in professional commitment between male and female Primary School Teachers.
2. There exist no significant difference in professional commitment between Probationary and Regular Primary School Teachers.
3. There exists no significant difference in professional commitment between Urban and Rural Primary School Teachers.

1.5. Operational definitions

The different key terms used in the title of the study and to be used in the body of study is operationally defined as follows;

1. Professional Commitment- Professional commitment of school teachers relates to their dedication, responsibility, and involvement in their field. It refers to their commitment to go above and beyond fundamental job responsibilities in order to strengthen learning for pupils, academic results, and the school environment.

2. Teacher- In this study the term teacher refers to teachers teaching in primary school i.e from class I to V.

1.6. Delimitation of the study

The present study was delimited in the following aspects:

1. The state of Sikkim has Six Districts. The study was restricted to only two District i.e. East District and North District of the state.
2. The study was delimited to the Primary School Teachers only.
3. The present study was delimited to 100 teachers.

2. Review of Literature

A review of related studies promotes a greater understanding of the problem and its crucial aspects and ensures the avoidance of unnecessary duplication. It is an indispensable part of any research project. It is also an important prerequisite to actual planning and then execution of any research work. The key to the vast house of published literature of India and abroad opens doors

of significant problems, explanatory hypothesis and provides helpful orientation, paving the way for the insights and much higher level of generalizations. Besides, it provides comparative data in this light of which the investigator enables to compare and interpret his findings. A researcher would know what is already known about the problem and how others have investigated it. A summary of the writing of recognized authorities and of previous researches provides evidence that the researcher is familiar with what is already known and what is still unknown and untested.

2.1. Studies Conducted in India

Shanthi and Devi (2021) Conducted study on Professional Commitment of Primary School Teachers. Normative Survey Method was used for the present study. A sample of 108 Primary School Teachers was selected in Coimbatore district by using Simple Random Sampling Technique. The data was analyzed through t-test and ANOVA. Major findings showed that there is a significant difference between Professional Commitment of teachers with respect to Experience also there is no significant difference between Professional Commitment of teachers with respect to Gender and Qualification.

Arya and Mehta (2024) Conducted student on Professional Commitment of Primary School Teachers in relation to Self Efficacy. The study consisted of 500 teachers teaching in government schools of Gujarat at the Primary level. Data was collected with the help of professional commitment scale for teachers by Baljeet Kaur (2007) and teacher self-efficacy scale by Ralf Schwarzer, Gerdamarie S. Schmitz and Gary T. Daytner (1999). The data obtained were analysed statistically with the help of Mean, SD, t-ratio and correlation to arrive at the following conclusions: (i) Female primary school teachers were found to have higher professional commitment than male school teachers. (ii) There is no significant gender difference was found in the self-efficacy of primary school teachers. (iii) There is positive correlation was found between professional commitment and self-efficacy.

2.2. Studies conducted Abroad

Yazici and Ozan (2024) Teachers' Level of Professional Commitment. The sample of the research consists of 608 teachers working in primary, middle, and high school schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in Yakutiye, Palandöken, and Aziziye districts of Erzurum province. As a data collection tool in the research; "The Personal Information Form" and "The Teachers' Professional Engagement Scale" were used. In the analysis of the data, descriptive analyses, Mann–Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis H test were used. The teachers' level of commitment to the profession did not show a significant difference according to the variables of age, marital status, professional seniority, and graduated faculty, but showed a significant difference according to the variables of gender and teaching level. It has been obtained that teachers' levels of commitment to the profession is very high. It has been determined that female teachers have higher levels of commitment to their profession. It has been concluded that primary school teachers' levels of commitment to the profession is higher than that of high school teachers. There was no significant difference according to age, marital status, professional seniority, or graduated faculty.

3. Method of the study

3.1. Design

The purpose of the study was to find out professional commitment among primary school teachers of Sikkim. Therefore the present study was based on the descriptive method.

3.2. Sample

The representative proportion of the population is called a sample. The sample of 100 primary school teachers was selected from Gangtok and Mangan District of Sikkim. Out of 100 teachers 50 male and 50 female, 50 probationary and 50 regular, 50 urban and 50 rural teachers were selected. The sample was collected by way of Random Sampling Techniques.

Table 3.1: The Distribution of the Sample

Sl. No.	Independent Variables	Categories	N	Total Sample
1	Gender	Male	50	100
		Female	50	
2	Job Types	Probationary	50	100
		Regular	50	
3	Locality	Rural	50	100
		Urban	50	

3.3. Tools used

The investigator used Dr. Ravinder Kaur, Dr. Sarbjit Kaur Ranu and Mrs. Sarvjeet Kaur Brar's (2011), "Professional Commitment Scale for Teachers" 2011. The tool has 45 items and was rated in a five rating scale. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree.

3.4. The Procedure of the Study

Data were collected from the Primary Schools Teachers of Gangtok and Mangan District of Sikkim. Here the researcher used standardized tools in order to collect the information regarding Professional Commitment among Primary School Teachers of Sikkim. The questionnaires were distributed to 100 primary school teachers. The data collected was scored, analyzed and interpreted as per the manual and finally, interpretation of data was done.

3.5. Statistical treatment of the collected data

In the present study, descriptive statistical techniques were employed for collection of data. To assess professional commitment among primary school teachers of Sikkim the important statistical measures mostly used were Mean, SD and t-test.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The data may be adequate, valid and reliable to any extent, it does not serve any worthwhile purpose unless it is carefully edited, systematically classified and tabulated, scientifically analyzes, intelligently interpreted and rationally concluded.

4.1. ORGANIZATION OF DATA

After having administered the test, the investigator assessed the answer sheets. The test was scored so that statistical treatment could possible.

4.2. ANALYSIS OF DATA

The details of the analysis of data collected from the selected sample on Professional Commitment among Primary School Teachers of Sikkim are presented as under.

4-2.1. Comparison of Attitude towards Professional Commitment among Male and Female Primary School Teachers

The obtained statistics pertaining to significance of difference between mean scores of male and female primary school teachers have been given in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: t-value of male and female primary school teachers in respect of their attitude towards Professional Commitment

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remark
Male	50	192.86	7.20	.362	Not significant
Female	50	193.34	5.98		

Fig. no. 1: Bar Graph showing the mean value of Male and Female Primary Teachers towards Professional Commitment

The mean scores, S.Ds and 't' values of Professional Commitment concern to male and female Primary Teachers are incorporated in table no 4.1. It can be understood that 't' values belongs to male and female Primary Teachers on Professional Commitment is not significant.

It is also clearly depicted from the figure no. 1, that mean value of male and female teachers almost do coincide, which indicate the fact that scores are normally distributed.

Hence, it may be inferred that male and female Primary School Teachers of Sikkim exhibits more or less similar attitude towards their Professional Commitment.

Therefore, the null hypothesis frame for Professional Commitment states that, *there is no significant difference in professional commitment between male and female primary school teachers* is accepted.

4-2.2. Comparison of Attitude towards Professional Commitment among Probationary and Regular School Teachers

The obtained statistics pertaining to significance of difference between mean scores of Probationary and Regular school teachers have been given in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: t-value of Probationary and Regular primary school teachers in respect of their attitude towards Professional Commitment

Job Types	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remark
Probationary	50	193.46	6.45	.544	Not significant
Regular	50	192.74	6.77		

Fig. no. 2: Bar Graph showing the mean value of Probationary and Regular Primary Teachers towards Professional Commitment

The mean scores, S.Ds and 't' values of Professional Commitment concern to Probationary and Regular Primary Teachers are incorporated in table no 4.1. It can be understood that 't' values belongs to Probationary and Regular Primary Teachers on Professional Commitment is not significant.

It is also clearly depicted from the figure no. 2, that mean value of Probationary and Regular primary teachers almost do coincide, which indicate the fact that scores are normally distributed.

Hence, it may be inferred that Probationary and Regular Primary School Teachers of Sikkim exhibits more or less similar attitude towards their Professional Commitment.

Therefore, the null hypothesis frame for Professional Commitment states that, *there exist no significant difference in professional commitment between Probationary and regular primary school teachers* is accepted.

4-2.3. Comparison of Attitude towards Professional Commitment among Rural and Urban Primary School Teachers

The obtained statistics pertaining to significance of difference between mean scores of Rural and Urban primary school teachers have been given in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: t-value of Rural and Urban school teachers in respect of their attitude towards Professional Commitment

Locality	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remark
Rural	50	192.64	6.98	.723	Not significant
Urban	50	183.56	5.66		

Fig. no 3: Bar Graph showing the mean value of Rural and Urban Primary Teachers towards Professional Commitment

The mean scores, S.Ds and 't' values of Professional Commitment concern to Rural and Urban Primary Teachers are incorporated in table no 4.1. It can be understood that 't' values belongs to Rural and Urban Teachers on Professional Commitment is not significant.

It is also clearly depicted from the figure no. 2, that there is a slight difference in the mean value of Rural and Urban primary school teachers which indicates that Rural Teachers' attitude towards professional commitment is better than urban teachers.

Therefore, the null hypothesis frame for Professional Commitment states that, *there exist no significant difference in professional commitment between Rural and Urban primary school teachers* is accepted.

5.13. Conclusion

A competent and committed teacher is one of the most crucial factors in the success of any education system. A teacher who is truly committed to students is one that puts students' learning and interests above everything else. In the present study an attempt was made by the researcher to study professional commitment among primary school teacher. The findings of the study suggested that there exist no difference in the male and female, probationary and regular, rural and urban primary school teachers with respect to professional commitment. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that Male and female, probationary and regular, rural and urban secondary school teachers are equally committed towards their profession.

5.14. Educational Implication

Educational Implications are recommended as follows:

1. There is needful requirement of workshops in the educational institutions which promote work culture among primary school teachers.

2. There has to be a regular appreciation of good performance of teachers and there should be appraisals in the form of increments/recognition/rewards.
3. There is a conscious necessity of checking the salary status of teachers so as to ensure that they get the prescribed salary under rules.
4. The promotional opportunities can only be made available to each teacher keeping in view the transparency of evaluation criteria.
5. Management of schools should always develop effective monitoring strategies to ensure the professional commitment of all teachers.
6. Participatory, innovative methods and techniques of teaching should be effectively enforced among teachers to ensure students interest.
7. School authorities should identify the ways and means through which teachers can be provided with facilitating work environment which will influence their work and also commitment towards teaching. Satisfaction from the job is necessary for full devotion and commitment of teachers towards the profession.
8. Teachers should be adequately motivated by the government by way of proper remuneration for teacher effectiveness.

5.15. Suggestion for further Research

Suggestions for further research are given below:

1. The present study can be conducted at different levels of education such as, elementary, secondary and college level.
2. The present study can be conducted with many other variables such as job satisfaction, task environment in the school, leadership roles teaching competency etc.

3. A comparative research study of classroom management involving private school teachers and government schools teachers need to be undertaken with respect to their professional commitment.

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